

Development of a Motion Tracking Interface Using Wireless Inertial Measurement Units for Biomedical Purposes

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Abstract— This article discusses the development of an interface designed to represent the attitude and heading of wireless inertial measurement units (IMUs). The long-term goal is to build a real-time human motion tracking system by using a combination of IMUs that communicate with each other, establishing a wireless body area network (WBAN). In this context, the objective of this paper is to describe the techniques applied to our software to meet the described requirements, showing and discussing the current interface situation and the next steps of the project. The outcome was a wireless motion-tracking interface designed for a single-joint structure, employing two IMUs in parallel to capture movement data.

Keywords — *Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), Real-Time, Network, Multithreading*

I. INTRODUCTION

This article presents the development of an interface designed to represent the attitude and heading of wireless inertial measurement units (IMUs). The long-term vision is to create a real-time human motion tracking system that combines multiple IMUs communicating wirelessly, forming a body area network (WBAN).

Human motion tracking has broad applications, ranging from use as a controller in electronic circuits to athletic training, animation production, rehabilitation, health diagnostics, biomechanical analysis, and even bio-inspired robotics [1][2][3]. Due to joint movement precision and acuity being easily affected by physiological, anatomical, and environmental factors, precise tools for kinematic and biomechanical analysis are essential for understanding and improving movement performance.

A variety of motion capture systems exist, including mechanical, acoustical, optical, magnetic, and inertial approaches [1][4]. Each has its own strengths and limitations. Inertial sensing stands out as a lightweight, cost-effective, and compact solution, making it particularly well-suited for the type of application targeted by our research group [1][5].

Prior to the work described here, the group developed and validated an inertial tracking system [5][6]. This system integrates a tri-axial gyroscope, accelerometer, and magnetometer, with data acquired via the SPI protocol by an ESP32-C3 microcontroller. The microcontroller assembles the sensor data into a payload and transmits it via Wi-Fi to a dedicated router. The interface software described in this article runs on a computer connected to that router through an Ethernet link. Figure 1 presents a diagram of the developed system.

Fig. 1. Inertial tracking system diagram. Translated from Souza et al., 2024

Accurately determining the physical orientation of the IMU requires fusing signals from the three sensors [7][8]. This process must also address challenges such as drift

in integrated gyroscope and accelerometer data [9][10], magnetic interference affecting magnetometer readings [10], and limitations in speed, accuracy, and robustness [11][12]. Over the years, various algorithms—such as the Extended Kalman filter and the Madgwick filter—have been developed to tackle these issues [13][14][15][16].

The interface developed in this work was designed to receive and decode data from the router, perform sensor fusion on the three-axis measurements from each IMU, and visualize their orientation through virtual objects in a graphical user interface (GUI). This process is repeated for all active sensors, with a response time that approaches real-time performance.

By presenting the current state of the interface and discussing the techniques applied in its implementation, this paper aims to provide a clear view of the progress achieved so far, as well as the next steps toward building a fully functional wireless motion tracking system, described in Figure 2 — Each IMU is positioned at strategic locations on the body, enabling its orientation measurements to be correlated with those of adjacent sensors in order to compute the body joint angles across the three axes (x, y, and z).

Fig. 2. Desired WBAN system scheme

II. METHODOLOGY

This section will be divided into three subsections: the first describes the firmware-router and router-software communication interface and decode process; the second section presents the data processing strategies, as the change to quaternion representation and the data fusion algorithm used; finally, the third section deals with the GUI and the concurrent programming structure to meet the response time for multiple sensors.

A. Communication

2.1.1 Main Communication Concepts Definitions

- **Transmission Control Protocol (TCP)**

TCP is a connection-oriented communication protocol, which means it follows a defined set of rules to establish,

negotiate, manage, and terminate a connection between two devices. This protocol organizes data into packets for transmission between a server and a client [17].

One of TCP's key features is its acknowledgment mechanism and various control methods that ensure data and messages are delivered reliably. Additionally, TCP monitors network traffic to keep the number of packets below a threshold that could degrade performance [17] [18] [19].

Because TCP operates over a packet-switched network—where no dedicated circuit is established before sending data—it must handle challenges such as packets arriving out of order or getting lost during transmission [19].

- **User Datagram Protocol (UDP)**

UDP is a simple, connectionless protocol that provides raw data delivery without mechanisms to verify data integrity, ensure packet order, or confirm receipt [20].

It is commonly used by applications that prioritize speed over reliability, such as those requiring fast transmission of control commands or similar time-sensitive data [19] [21].

- **Socket Communication**

The socket is an abstract data structure that allows two programs, usually running on different sets of hardware over a network, to exchange data, acting as an endpoint to this link [22]. In a specific application, it must be defined, within the structure, parameters such as the address family, the Internet Protocol (IP) address itself, port number and transport protocol (TCP and UDP, for example).

2.1.2 Firmware-Router Interface

The firmware-router interface corresponds to the data transmission structure from each sensor through the Wi-Fi client router. Figure 3 shows a flowchart of the firmware operation.

Fig. 3. Firmware Flowchart. Translated from Souza et al., 2023

Let's walk through the flowchart. When the sensor is initialized and connected to the network, the code sets up a dedicated TCP server for that sensor. Each server is assigned a unique port number corresponding to its sensor ID (1, 2, 3, etc.), guaranteeing a dedicated server for each sensor. Additionally, the sensors create a single UDP server responsible for sending configuration parameters to the router. These parameters include the current IMU state (INIT, HOLD, or RUN), the signal's sampling rate, and which sensors are active: A (accelerometer only), AG (accelerometer and gyroscope), or AGM (accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer) [5].

When the GUI's 'start' button is pressed, it sends a start announcement packet, triggering the system to begin operation. As the sample timer starts, data packets of 870 bytes are filled with 29-byte samples collected at 500 Hz [5].

2.1.3 Router-Software Interface

Figure 4 presents the Router-Software architecture. Upon initialization, the software detects the number of sensors connected to the network and creates a TCP socket for each one. Each socket is assigned a port calculated as $X + n$, where X is a fixed constant and n corresponds to the sensor's unique ID (1, 2, 3, 4, etc.).

Each socket is managed by its dedicated thread (the concept of threads is explained in detail in section 2.3). The thread reads the first byte of every payload to determine how to decode the data, since the payload length varies depending on the amount of sensor information transmitted.

Once decoded, an object called *ImuData* is created for each IMU. This object contains the sensor's ID, sample index, timestamp, and the measurements from the accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer along all three axes.

Fig. 4. Router-Software Interface Diagram

B. Data Processing

This subsection is divided into 2 segments. The first one details the main numerical systems used to describe the orientation of three dimensional objects (*Euler* angles and Quaternions); these concepts are crucial to comprehend the data fusion algorithm that is described in the second segment.

2.2.1 Euler Angles and Quaternions

Euler's rotation theorem states that, in three-dimensional space, any rotation of a rigid body can be described with three angles; those angles are called the Euler angles [1][23][24]. Equations 1 to 6 describes how those angles are acquired:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} = R \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where

$$R = R_\psi R_\theta R_\phi \quad (2)$$

$$R_\psi = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ -\sin \psi & \cos \psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$R_\theta = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ 0 & -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$R_\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

So

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi \cos \phi - \sin \psi \cos \theta \sin \phi & \cos \psi \sin \phi + \sin \psi \cos \theta \cos \phi & \sin \psi \sin \theta \\ -\sin \psi \cos \phi - \cos \psi \cos \theta \sin \phi & -\sin \psi \sin \phi + \cos \psi \cos \theta \cos \phi & \cos \psi \sin \theta \\ \sin \theta \sin \phi & -\sin \theta \cos \phi & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

To simplify, the angles ψ , θ , and ϕ represent the rotations of a rigid body around the original x , y , and z axes, transforming them into new coordinate axes x_1 , x_2 , and x_3 through the rotation matrix R .

While this Euler angle system provides an intuitive and practical way to express rotational data, it suffers from a well-known limitation called gimbal lock [24]. The name comes from the mechanical analogy of three nested gimbals—rings mounted on pivots at right angles. When the outer gimbal rotates in certain ways, two of the inner gimbals can become aligned, effectively "locking" them together and causing the loss of one degree of freedom in rotation [24][1].

To overcome this issue and provide a robust alternative for representing 3D rotations, the Irish mathematician William Rowan Hamilton introduced quaternions in 1844 [25]. Quaternions extend into four-dimensional hypercomplex numbers that elegantly describe orientation and rotation in 3D space without suffering from gimbal lock.

Equations 7 and 8 illustrate the quaternion's structure: a four-dimensional vector q , where the component a is the real part and b , c and d form the imaginary parts [25].

$$q = a + bi + cj + dk \quad (7)$$

Where

$$i^2 = j^2 = k^2 = ijk = -1 \quad (8)$$

Specifically, if θ is a rotation angle and the unit vector $(v_x, v_y, v_z)^T$ represents a rotation axis, its quaternion elements a , b , c and d are [1]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \\ d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(0.5\theta) \\ v_x \sin(0.5\theta) \\ v_y \sin(0.5\theta) \\ v_z \sin(0.5\theta) \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

For orientation systems, the most important outcome that the quaternions properties can provide is that a quaternion q_i^b can be used to rotate any three element vector v_1 accordingly Equation 10 [1]:

$$v_b = q_i^b \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ v_1 \end{pmatrix} (q_i^b)^{-1} \quad (10)$$

In which:

- v_b is the rotated vector;
- q_i^b is a quaternion that converts a vector from the coordinate systems i to b ;
- v_i is the original vector;
- $q_i^{b^{-1}}$ is the conjugated quaternion of q_i^b ,
if $q_i^b = (a, b, c, d)$, then $q_i^{b^{-1}} = (a, -b, -c, -d)$

Equation 10 basically tells us that if we have two quaternions from 2 different coordinate references, e.g. two quaternions $q_1 = (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1)^T$ and $q_2 = (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2)^T$ that describe the orientation of its respective IMU, we can calculate the quaternion that describes the rotations needed to q_1 have the same orientation as q_2 , hence the relative angles to them by the multiplication of q_1 by q_2^{-1} . As Equation 11 shows, a quaternion multiplication is composed of a simple combination of additions and multiplications of its components [25].

$$q_1 q_2 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 a_2 - b_1 b_2 - c_1 c_2 - d_1 d_2 \\ a_1 b_2 + b_1 a_2 + c_1 d_2 - d_1 c_2 \\ a_1 c_2 - b_1 d_2 + c_1 a_2 + d_1 b_2 \\ a_1 d_2 + b_1 c_2 - c_1 b_2 + d_1 a_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

2.2.2 The Madgwick Filter

After obtaining all the information of a specific IMU in the ImuData object format and converting the digital raw values of accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer to its

respective physical measurement units ($m/s^2, rad/s$ and μT), those values are used in a magnetic, angular-rate and gravity (MARG) signals fusion algorithm, developed by Sebastian Madgwick and commonly known as the "Madgwick Filter" [15].

Essentially, the filter has magnetic distortion compensation and gyroscope drift compensation methods connected to each other, dependent on the accelerometer and magnetometer reads, as well as the last orientation quaternion estimation sample. About this estimated quaternion itself, these two correction processes are incorporated into a gradient descent algorithm, responsible for finding the smallest rotation that aligns the measured gravity and magnetic field to the predicted ones (assuming a calibrated earth frame reference) [15]. The result is an optimized orientation quaternion output [1].

C. GUI and concurrent programming structure

Figure 4 already indicates that our software sets multiple streams of execution for each IMU connected to the system, and also shows that these processes are also separated based on their network origin (TCP or UDP server). This software characteristic is based on the concept of a multithreaded architecture.

A multithreaded architecture is one in which the machine's CPU executes multiple processes, each one separated into different threads (a unit of sequential code processing) without the aid of software context switches [26] [27].

As indicated in section 2.1.3, the software is divided into two network-based main processes (UDP and TCP). The UDP process is responsible for the transmission of the configuration and state of the GUI and the sensors to allow data flow through the TCP channel. This process, on the other hand, is responsible for being the IMU's sensor data stream, having a single thread responsible for each device's information transfer up to the GUI.

III. RESULTS

Figure 5 shows a picture of the interface running on a laptop, The current version of the GUI adopts a model of a single rotational joint object to simulate the movement of an arm. In order to emulate elbow flexion and extension, a knee orthosis prototype was used.

In addition, a dedicated setup was developed for the individual analysis of each sensor, as illustrated in Figure 6. This configuration enables a more precise inspection of the nine sensor plots, while simultaneously providing the corresponding quaternion values (referenced to the Earth frame), updated at the same rate as the sensor's graphical representation and the associated plots.

Fig. 5. Interface framework. (a) Sensor configuration control window: allows users to select the main reference sensor and data source via dropdown menus, set the sample rate and data window length, monitor the number of bytes transferred through an updating grid, and control data acquisition with 'Run' and 'Stop' buttons. (b) Sensor graphical window: features nine real-time plots displaying sensor readings (ax, ay, az, gx, gy, gz, mx, my, mz) corresponding to the selected sensor. (c) Sensor object window: presents a 3D visualization of the sensor's orthotic structure, with blue rectangles representing the IMUs. (d) Overview of the IMUs utilized during the test.

Fig. 6. Setup Interface framework. (a) Quaternion window, the variables i , j and k are the same as displayed in Eq. 7. the W variable corresponds to the quaternion real part a

The interface was intentionally limited to managing a maximum of two sensors simultaneously to facilitate the analysis of warnings and errors. Despite this restriction, the system struggled to maintain satisfactory performance at a 500 Hz sample rate. It was necessary to reduce the sampling frequency to 100 Hz to achieve smooth object movement and prevent interface freezing.

IV. DISCUSSION

The use of the recommended tools for the development of this kind of system turned to similar outcomes as the ones described in literature, despite some minor differences in hardware specifications and required performance [1] [2] [7].

Given the complications related to system speed and the fact that, at higher frequencies, the system did not behave satisfactorily—occasionally freezing and causing the interface to crash — It is still necessary to reduce the frequency at which the collected data are processed

and displayed on the screen. A promising strategy consists in accumulating the sensor values in a circular buffer and performing the processing and visualization at a lower frequency, but with larger data batches rather than sample-by-sample updates. This approach constitutes one of the forthcoming steps, in addition to increasing the number of sensors operating simultaneously and developing new graphical representation objects for the WBAN.

V. CONCLUSION

By integrating a network-based multithreaded architecture with a computationally efficient and robust numerical representation, quaternions and employing a noise-resistant, low-tuning data fusion algorithm such as the Madgwick filter, we successfully developed a promising wireless motion tracking interface.

However, to realize a fully operational Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN), further software enhancements are required. These include configuring the system for a predetermined number of sensors and implementing code optimization techniques to meet the desired performance standards.

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